

IMPLEMENTATION OF INDONESIAN LANGUAGE KNOWLEDGE ASSESSMENT IN INCLUSION CLASSES

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Abstract— *Assessment in the education process is a component that cannot be separated from other components, especially learning. Assessment result of learning by educators is the process of collecting information / data on the achievement of learning the participant students. Assessment result of study participants learners include competence attitude, knowledge and skills that do are impartial. The results of assessment are used to perform an evaluation of the completeness study participant students and the effectiveness of the process of learning. The essence and technique of assessment in the eyes of subjects Language Indonesia prepared in an effort to facilitate the educator in order to carry out the assessment in quality towards the achievement of learning outcomes of students at the elementary level. Assessment of knowledge that is done must be in line with the target in the curriculum of 2013 based competence. The research is focused on the assessment of knowledge the eyes of subjects Languages Indonesia with the subject of studi teacher language Indonesia and special assistant teacher. The research was conducted by interview, observation and documentation. The research subjects were Indonesian Language subject teachers and Special Companion Teachers. The results of the study concluded that the assessment of knowledge in Indonesian language subjects uses written test techniques, oral tests, and assignments.*

Keywords - *knowledge assessment, Indonesian language lessons, inclusive classes*

1. Introduction

In human life education is number one in individual personal development. Education is a person's life-long learning experience that is carried out consciously to improve certain abilities, knowledge, understanding and or skills. Increased knowledge can be carried out during the learning process that takes place carried out by educators. Educators must have special skills related to learning planning, implementation of learning, and assessment of learning outcomes.

Assessment of learning outcomes by educators is the process of gathering information / data about learning outcomes in aspects of attitude, aspects of knowledge, and aspects of skills carried out in a planned and systematic manner carried out to monitor the process, learning progress and improvement of learning outcomes through assignments and evaluation of learning outcomes. By knowing the weaknesses and strengths of students, the educator has a clear direction about what must be improved and can reflect on what he did in the learning process.

The nature and technique of evaluating groups of Indonesian language subjects is prepared in an effort to facilitate educators and educational units to be able to carry out quality assessments on the achievement of learning outcomes of students at the elementary education level.

In line with the characteristics of the competency-based curriculum that is oriented to competency mastery, the assessment system applied is in the form of a competency-based assessment system. Thus the standard of educational assessment for competency-based curriculum is a standard assessment system that is oriented to the level of mastery of

competencies targeted in the curriculum. Standards for assessing education can be achieved when there are standard rules regarding the educational assessment system that is applied at every level of education, both concerning the basis, principles, objectives, and assessment strategies.

2. Discussion

A. Knowledge Assessment

a) Definition of Knowledge Assessment

Knowledge assessment is an assessment carried out to determine the mastery of students which includes factual, conceptual, and procedural knowledge and low to high level thinking skills. Knowledge assessment is carried out with various assessment techniques. The teacher chooses assessment techniques that are in accordance with the competency characteristics assessed.

Assessment begins with the preparation of the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP). Knowledge assessment in addition to knowing whether students have achieved *mastery learning*, also to identify weaknesses and strengths in mastering students' knowledge in the learning process (*diagnostic*). Providing feedback (*feedback*) to students and teachers is very important, so the results of the assessment can be immediately used to improve the quality of learning. The results of the assessment of knowledge carried out during and after the learning process are expressed in the form of numbers.

b) Knowledge Assessment Techniques

Various knowledge assessment techniques can be used in accordance with the characteristics of each basic competency (KD). The techniques commonly used include written tests, oral tests, and assignments.

Table of Knowledge Assessment Techniques

Technique	Instrument's Shape	Goal	Ket.
Written test	True match, False, multiple choice, fill / complete, Essay	Knowing the mastery of students' knowledge to improve the learning process and / or value taking	Core Competence 3
Oral test	Question and answer	Check students' understanding to improve the learning process	Core Competencies 3 and 4
Assignment	Tasks carried out individually or in groups	Facilitating mastery of knowledge (if given during the learning process) or knowing mastery of knowledge (if given at the end of learning)	Core Competencies 3 and 4

- Prepare questions, commands that are delivered verbally.

e) Assignment

Assignment is the assignment of assignments to students to measure and / or facilitate students to acquire or increase knowledge. Assignment of the function to do after learning assessment (*assessment of learning*). While the assignment as an assignment method aims to increase the knowledge given before and / or the learning process (*assessment for learning*). Tasks can be done individually or in groups according to the characteristics of the assignments given, which are carried out at school, at home and outside of school.

Knowledge assessment scheme

c) Written Test

A written test is a test where questions and answers are presented in writing in the form of multiple choices, filling, right-wrong, matchmaking, and description. Written test instruments are developed by following the steps: a. set test objectives, b. compile the grid, c. write questions based on the grid and rules for writing questions, d. compile a scoring guide.

d) Oral Tests

Oral tests in the form of questions, orders, quizzes given by educators verbally and students respond to questions tersebut verbally. Answers to oral tests can be words, phrases, sentences or paragraphs. Oral tests aim to foster a bold attitude of opinion, check the mastery of knowledge for learning, confidence and the ability to communicate effectively.

The steps for implementing an oral test are as follows:

- Conduct analysis of basic competencies in accordance with the content of the lesson.
- Arrange the grid that will be a guide to making questions, commands that must be answered by students verbally.

B. Purpose and Function of Assessment

Assessment of learning outcomes by educators aims to monitor the process and learning progress of students and to increase the effectiveness of learning activities. Therefore, the assessment of learning outcomes by educators is carried out continuously and covers all aspects of students, both cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects in accordance with the characteristics of Indonesian language subjects.

Assessment by the education unit is the final assessment at the level of the education unit that aims to assess the achievement of SKL. The assessment of Indonesian Language subject groups is based on the results of national examinations taking into account the results of the assessment by educators. Assessment by educational units is used as: (a) one of the graduation requirements of students from the education unit, (b) the basis for improving the performance of educators, and (c) the basis for evaluating the implementation of the education unit level curriculum.

Class assessment is a process that is carried out through planning steps, preparation of assessment tools, collection of information through a number of evidences that show the achievement of student learning outcomes, processing, and use of information about student learning outcomes in accordance with indicators, competency standards, and basic

competencies. Thus, class assessments are carried out through various techniques / methods, such as performance evaluation, written assessment (paper and pencil test) or verbal, project assessment, product assessment, assessment through a collection of work / student work (portfolio), and self-assessment conforms to the demands of the indicator. (Ministry of National Education, 2006).

Assessment has the following functions. 1). Describing the extent to which a student has mastered a competency. 2). Evaluating student learning outcomes in order to help students understand their abilities, make decisions about the next step, both for program selection, personality development and for majors (as guidance). 3). Find learning difficulties and possible achievements that students can develop and as a diagnostic tool that helps educators determine whether a person needs to attend remedial or enrichment. 4). Find weaknesses and shortcomings of the ongoing learning process to improve the next learning process. 5). As a control for educators and educational units about the progress of student development.

3. Assessment of Indonesian Language Learning

Assessment of Indonesian language learning is carried out in various ways, namely written tests (*paper and pencil tests*), oral tests, and assessment of student work outcomes through a collection of work results (assignments). In accordance with the knowledge assessment techniques contained in the 2013 curriculum.

In basic competencies in Indonesian language lessons there are aspects of listening, speaking, reading and writing so that it is possible to conduct knowledge assessments with written test techniques, oral tests and assignments. In the implementation of language learning in schools, especially Indonesian, learning and research listen / listen, receive less attention as well as other language skills. Not necessarily all language teachers specifically teach listening or doing special listening / listening assessments. to students in a certain period. As the name implies, namely the assessment of listening / listening skills, or more precisely oral comprehension, the test material tested is delivered verbally and accepted by the student through the means of hearing. The problem that arises immediately is what means should be used and how to deliver effective assessments should we use recording media or be directly delivered (read out) verbally by the teacher when the test takes place.

Speaking skills have a lot in common with writing skills. Both are productive skills that are integrated. Productive, meaning that when speaking people use language to produce a (conversation). Called integrated meaning, the conversation occurs because of the incorporation of a number of abilities which are components of speech skills.

Reading activity is a mental activity to understand what is told by other parties through writing facilities. If in listening to the required knowledge of the sound system of the language in question, in reading activities required knowledge of the writing system, especially concerning letters and spelling. In essence letters or writing are only symbols of certain language sounds. Therefore, in reading activities we must recognize, that the writing symbol represents certain sounds that also contain certain meanings. Type of reading which is often used in teaching Indonesian, namely effective reading speed tests. Effective speed reading (KEM) according to Slamet Ahmad H. (1997) is a reader speeds achieved by formula number of words divided by the length of time required and peresentase scores were obtained.

At first writing ability is the ability to recognize and write sound symbols, write words and give birth to sentence structures. However, step by step students are introduced and tested for writing as a complete and coherent ability. To assess the most direct writing ability is of course by telling students to write, in the sense that they are given the task of writing an essay.

4. Inclusion Class

Inclusive education according to Sugiarnin (2009), namely education carried out by the School / Class involving all students without exception includes: Children who have language differences, Children who are at risk of dropping out of school due to illness, malnutrition and not performing well, Children of different religions, children with HIV / Aids, and children who are of school age but not in school, they are educated and provided with appropriate educational services in a friendly and compassionate way without discrimination.

Inclusive education is not merely the inclusion of extraordinary children / children with special needs to public schools, but rather is oriented towards how these educational services are provided in order to meet the needs of every child with the uniqueness and diversity that they naturally have.

Inclusive education can be interpreted as how education services are very meaningful in developing the potential and competency of all different children so that they can develop optimally according to the rhythm of their development. The learning settings are created friendly and fun.

Talking about inclusive classes is inseparable from the curriculum which is a reference in the learning process and assessment of learning outcomes. Curriculum adjustments are carried out by emphasizing the fulfillment of learning needs that are tailored to the child's abilities. Inclusive education demands curriculum adjustments in terms of time mastery of a number of learning materials. The curriculum in inclusive classes includes general curriculum, modified curriculum, and individualized curriculum. In terms of the use of the curriculum submitted to the school as an organizer of inclusive education. The use of the

curriculum as a reference for the implementation of inclusive education will influence the assessment process.

5. Research Method

Researchers tried to organize and sort data systematically records of observations, interviews, and others to improve the understanding of researchers about the case under study. This is consistent with what Bogdan and Biklen argued that data analysis is an effort carried out by working with data, organizing data, sorting it into manageable units, synthesizing it, finding and discovering what is important and what is learned, and deciding what can be told to others.

A. Data Collection Techniques

The instrument of data collection in this study is based on the type of data needed, to photograph the factual conditions regarding the evaluation of learning of children with special needs in inclusive settings in the field currently used with interviewing techniques, observation and documentation studies. This study will photograph the factual conditions regarding the evaluation of learning of children with special needs in inclusive schools that occur in the field today. The researcher hopes to produce data or facts that will become material or data in the formulation of the model development plan.

B. Data Analysis Techniques

Researchers tried to organize and sort data systematically records of observations, interviews, and others to improve the understanding of researchers about the case under study. This is consistent with what Bogdan and Biklen argued that data analysis is an effort carried out by working with data, organizing data, sorting it into manageable units, synthesizing it, finding and discovering what is important and what is learned, and deciding what can be told to others. The data contained in this study are qualitative data generated through interviews with Indonesian language subject teachers and

special education teachers in inclusive classes, documentation and direct observation in schools. Furthermore, these data are expressed in the form of descriptive narratives to describe the events experienced by the subject. The purpose of this analysis is to describe the factual and accurate occurrence of the facts that occurred during the study at Al-Biruni Junior High School

C. Tables

To find out the situation of children with special needs at the Al-Biruni education center, data is obtained as shown in the table.

Table of data for inclusive students at Al Biruni Junior High School

No.	Name of GDPK	Class	Specificity
1.	ADSG	7A	Mental Retardation
2.	BRP	7A	Autism
3.	DRR	7A	Mental Retardation
4.	FRS	7A	Mental Retardation
5.	MHNA	7A	ADD
6.	MZF	7A	Mental Retardation
7.	AA	7A	Mental Retardation
8.	ISB	7A	ADHD
9.	MAF	7A	Autism
10.	AKM	8A	Mental Retardation
11.	RFN	8A	Mental Retardation
12.	MZ	8A	Slow learner
13.	MNZ	8A	Mental Retardation
14.	FS	9A	Mental Retardation
15.	MAF	9A	Mental Retardation
16.	FS	9A	Autism
17.	DW	9A	ADHD
18.	FH	9A	Autism
19.	LSH	9A	Slow learner

6. Discussion

Based on the data collected through observation, interviews and documentation, the implementation of the knowledge assessment in Al-Biruni inclusion school refers to the curriculum agreed upon by the school. Where every child with special needs uses a different curriculum that is tailored to their needs. Be it children who use the general / regular curriculum, modified curriculum and individualized curriculum.

Assessment of learning outcomes by educators is carried out continuously to monitor the process, progress and improvement of academic and non-academic learning outcomes. Furthermore, the assessment is used to assess the achievement of student competencies, the material for preparing progress reports on learning outcomes and improving the learning process.

Knowledge assessment techniques carried out in inclusive organizers' schools go through written tests which are assessment techniques that require written answers. The second is an oral test that is a test in the form of a question or quiz given orally by the educator and students respond to the question verbally. The third is assignment, namely assigning assignments to students to measure and / or facilitate students

to gain or increase knowledge. The number of questions given to students is adjusted to the abilities and curriculum used by these students.

6. Conclusion

Assessment must measure cold objectives achieved in accordance with the exposure of indicators and learning objectives in the learning plan. In addition, the assessment also needs to be carried out with the selection of the right form. If we want an assessment of knowledge and assessing skills, then the chosen form of performance appraisal with the right format tool, this avoids biased results. However, the tools made are adjusted to the level of ability and breadth of the desired curriculum.

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